

Effect of Extraction Solvent on Total Phenolics, Flavonoids and Antioxidant Capacity of Flower Bud and Foliage of *Calligonum polygonoides* L.

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Calligonum polygonoides L. (Phog) is an endemic perennial shrub of Thar Desert of Rajasthan (India) with dominant biomass and phenolic compounds (13-35% DWB) production capacity in its natural habitat. In the present study, water and different concentrations of ethanol, methanol and acetone (50%, 75% and 100%, respecting) were used for the extraction of phytochemicals from flower bud and foliages. Total phenolics, total flavonoids and total antioxidants of different extracts were investigated using various *in-vitro* assays. The extract obtained with 50% aqueous methanol exhibited highest phenolic content in flower bud. The 50% aqueous acetone extract exhibited highest phenolic, flavonoids and total antioxidant in foliages. From the results, it can be concluded that 50% aqueous mixture of acetone/methanol/ethanol might be the best suited extraction solvent for efficient extraction of phenolic compounds from *C. polygonoides*. These results on phenolic, flavonoids and antioxidant activity indicated that *C. polygonoides* can be used in dietary application through nutraceuticals or functional food with a potential to reduce the oxidative stress.

Key words: *Calligonum polygonoides*, total phenolic content, antioxidants activity, extraction solvent, food analysis

The ever changing living standard along with awareness towards healthy and balanced eating habit and to cope with stressful lifestyle has attracted the people towards phytochemicals rich foods. In recent time, it become a well-known fact that intake of natural antioxidant rich foods is correlated with lower risk of degenerative diseases, specifically cardiovascular diseases and cancer (1). In this respect plant based food comes first to provide plentiful natural phytochemicals with proved disease preventing and curing effects through their antioxidant, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive, anti-ageing, anti-allergic activities. In plant based bioactive compounds, phenolic compounds have most prominent place with widespread occurrence in plant kingdom as secondary metabolites with significant morpho-physiological effects on plant along with biological activity like antioxidant activity, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial etc. The phenolic compounds are attributed the antioxidant activity through scavenging of free radicals (2, 3). The chemical structure of phenolics

is made up of an aromatic ring and a hydroxyl group. On the basis of number of phenolic units, the number and location of hydroxyl groups and their derivatives, about 8000 different phenolic compounds are classified in three major groups such as phenolic acids as cinnamic acid derivatives, glycosidic phenylpropanoids and phenolic acids that occur as hydroxylated benzoic acid derivatives (4-6).

Calligonum polygonoides L. (Phog) is an endemic and threatened perennial shrub of 3-4 feet height with whitish, articulate and fragile branches. It is naturally grown shrub in the hot arid region of Thar Desert of Rajasthan. *C. polygonoides* is locally known as *Phog*, *Phogala* or *Phogaro* and belongs to the Polygonaceae family (7). It grows well under resource poor conditions where any type of vegetation is not possible. *C. polygonoides*, is a dominant biomass producer under extremes of multiple abiotic stresses at sandy areas of the hot arid desert (8). *C. polygonoides* has high economic value as its all tissues are being used for many purposes. Its abortive flowers and succulent fruits are the most important source of food for sustenance during frequently occurring

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famines which has cooling effect to the body and cure sun stroke (9-12). The aqueous paste of plant is used as an antidote against snake bite, heavy dose of opium and *Calotropis procera*. Some medicinal properties such as curing typhoid, asthma, cough and cold have also been reported (13, 14). Samejo *et al.* (15) reported the presence of different secondary metabolites *viz.* phenolics, flavonoids, tannin, steroids and terpenoids in different parts of phog plant. Its higher scavenging activity against DPPH, ABTS and superoxides along with anti-fungal and cytotoxicity has been reported with identification of some flavonoid compounds in flower buds (16-18). Recently, Berwal *et al.* (19) reported that different plant parts of phog possessed extremely higher values of phenolic content (13 to 35% on dry weight basis) along with very high values for flavonoids and total antioxidant capacity as well. In spite of these few studies on *C. polygonoides* scavenging properties have been done and no specific report is available on phenolics and flavonoids content anywhere in literature including two major international phenolic databases *viz.* i) Phenol-Explorer database (www.phenol-explorer.eu) and ii) USDA database for the flavonoids content of selected foods (20). Most of the studies on nutraceutical and medicinal properties of *C. polygonoides* are based on rural wisdom and ITKs.

Various techniques are used to recover the antioxidant compounds specifically phenolics from the plants like soxhlet apparatus, supercritical fluid extraction, subcritical water extraction, maceration, pestle mortal homogenization and ultrasound assisted extraction. However, recovery of these compounds depends on the extraction procedure and extraction solvent both (21). For recovery of polyphenols, aqueous mixtures of ethanol, methanol, acetone and ethyl acetate in different concentrations are most suitable. One extraction solvent which gives better yield for phenolic compounds from one plant source need not be true for other plant source too. Because, the structural difference in phenolic compounds in different plant sources also play a major role in determining their solubility in solvents of different polarity. For example in barley, mixture of ethanol and acetone has been found better solvent (22), while

aqueous ethanol performed better than aqueous methanol and aqueous acetone in flavonoids extraction from mate tea (23) and aqueous acetone was better in black tea (21). In general, ethanol has been taken as safe phenolic extractor because its intake is safe for human. But generally aqueous methanol has been found very effective for lower molecular weight phenolics, while aqueous acetone for the higher molecular weight phenolics (24). Therefore, extraction procedure as well as extraction solvent might have a great impact on phenolic yield from different plant sources. Keeping these views in mind, the present investigation was planned to optimize the extraction solvent for phenolic extraction from the flower bud and foliage of *C. polygonoides* which is a very rich source of phenolic compounds.

Materials and Methods

Plant material and chemicals: Flower buds and foliage of *C. polygonoides* used in this study were collected from the plants grown at research farm of ICAR-Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Bikaner, Rajasthan (India) and subjected to shade drying in laboratory. Dried samples were ground till fine powder using a kitchen milling machine and passed through a 100-mesh sieve. All the chemicals used in this study were purchased from Sigma-aldrich, Merck India and Hi-Media.

Sample preparations: Accurately weighed 100 mg of 100-mess fine sample powder and homogenized in a mortar and pestle with 5 ml of appropriate extraction solvent (Table 1) and incubated it at 70 °C in water bath for 1 h. After incubation the tubes were subjected to centrifugation at 10000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C

Table 1: Solvent systems used for phenolic compound extraction

Solvent Systems	
Water	
Ethanol	
	100% ethanol
	75% aqueous ethanol
	50% aqueous ethanol
Methanol	
	100% Methanol
	75% aqueous methanol
	50% aqueous methanol
Acetone	
	100% acetone
	75% aqueous acetone
	50% aqueous acetone

temperature, collected the supernatant. Re-extraction of the residue was done twice with 5 ml of respective extraction solvent and centrifuged. The supernatant was pooled and the volume was made up to 20 ml with respective solvent and stored at -20 °C till further use.

Total phenolic content (TPC): The total phenolic content (TPC) in different solvent extracts was estimated following Folin-Ciocalteu method described by Medini *et al.* (25) with some modifications. The total phenolic content in different solvent extracts was expressed as mg gallic acids equivalents (GAE)/100 g DW. All the extracts were analyzed in triplicate.

Total flavonoids content (TFC): Total flavonoids content (TFC) in different solvent extracts was estimated by aluminum chloride based spectrophotometric method described by Medini *et al.* (25). A volume of different extracts separately (1 ml) was mixed with 0.3 ml each of 5% NaNO₂ and 10% AlCl₃ and 3.4 ml of 1 M NaOH. The resultant reaction mixtures were incubated at room temperature for 15 minutes and measured the absorbance at 510 nm against the reagent blank. The total flavonoids content was expressed as catechole equivalent (Ct.E)/100g. The whole assays were carried out in triplicate in order to get mean value.

Total antioxidant activity: The reducing capacity of the extracts was assayed by CUPRAC methods described by Apak *et al.* (26) with minor adjustments. In this assay, simultaneously 1 ml each of cupric chloride (10 mM), ethanolic neocuproin (75 mM) and ammonium acetate (1 M, pH 7.0) mixed in test tubes containing 2 ml of distilled water followed by 100 µl extract. These mixtures were incubated in dark for 30 minutes at room temperature and measured the OD at 450 nm against the reagent blank. Ascorbic acid was taken as positive reference standard and uttered the results as mg AAE/100g. Whole assays were carried out in triplicate in order to get mean value.

Statistical analysis: The assays were carried out in triplicate and the results were standardized and expressed as mean values. The direction and magnitude of correlation between variables were performed with one way analysis of variance and *p*-values <0.01 were

regarded as significant. To assess the relationship between the activities of two different assays, Pearson's correlation coefficients (R) were calculated to determine their relationship.

Results and Discussion

Recently, plant based phytochemicals including phenolic compounds have received much attention due to their various health benefits to human being with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. Hence, the demand of many herbs is not only increased for culinary purpose but also as a supplement for functional foods. Therefore, the study on better extraction of these bio-active compounds along with their stability during the preparations of plant extracts would be very useful for selection of the most effective extraction showing variable efficacy with different plant sources (27). In other words, it is explained that one solvent which is better with one plant is not necessary to give similar results with other plant source due to the difference in phytochemical composition of different plant sources. This is not always true that antioxidant phytochemicals with diverse chemical distinctiveness and polarities are soluble in a particular solvent (28). In the present study, extraction of phenolic compounds from flower buds and foliages of phog plant in different concentrations of ethanol, methanol and acetone along with pure distilled water were used (Table 1). The composition of extraction solvents significantly (*p* < 0.01) affected the measured concentrations of phenolics, flavonoids and total antioxidant capacity in both the plant materials and also the effectiveness of different solvent composition was slightly different in flower bud and foliages.

Total phenolic content (TPC): TPC of flower bud and foliages of *C. polygonoides* in different solvent systems was assayed using FCR method. TPC values were obtained from the calibration curve and were expressed as mg GAE/g DW. The TPC values of flower buds in different solvent systems varied from 31.92 mg GAE/g DW in 100% acetone extract to 152.39 mg GAE/g DW in 50% methanol extract (Table 2), which decreased in the following order: 50% methanol > 50% acetone > 75% methanol > 50% ethanol > 75% ethanol > 75% acetone

Table 2: Effect of extraction solvent on TPC, TFC and TAA in *C. polygonoides* flower bud.

Solvent System*	TPC (mg GAE/g)	TFC (mg CE/g)	TAA (mg AAE/g)
Water	75.39 ^E	2.58 ^F	159.85 ^D
Ethanol			
100% ethanol	34.15 ^F	1.40 ^F	88.28 ^E
75% aqueous ethanol	125.87 ^U	4.19 ^U	296.20 ^B
50% aqueous ethanol	137.86 ^B	4.82 ^C	332.79 ^A
Methanol			
100% Methanol	104.35 ^D	3.77 ^E	253.05 ^C
75% aqueous methanol	140.28 ^B	4.33 ^U	291.26 ^B
50% aqueous methanol	152.39 ^A	4.33 ^U	330.90 ^A
Acetone			
100% acetone	31.92 ^F	1.79 ^U	94.77 ^F
75% aqueous acetone	124.27 ^C	5.55 ^B	338.21 ^A
50% aqueous acetone	142.45 ^B	6.03 ^A	351.97 ^A

*Expressed as fraction of solvents to water. TPC-Total phenolic content; TFC-Total flavonoids content; TTA-Total antioxidant activity; GAE-Gallic acid equivalent; CE-Catechin equivalent; AAE-Ascorbic acid equivalent. Different superscripted letters (A-H) indicate significant difference from one another (p < 0.01)

> 100% methanol > water > 100% ethanol > 100% acetone (Fig. 1A). The TPC of 50% acetone extract (142.45 mg GAE/g DW) is not significantly higher than 75% methanol extract (140.28 mg GAE/g DW) and 50% ethanol extract (137.86 mg GAE/g DW) and the TPC of 75% ethanol extract (125.87 mg GAE/g DW) was also significantly at par with that of 75% acetone extract (124.27 mg GAE/g DW) (p < 0.01). The TPC of water extract (75.39 mg GAE/g DW) was significantly higher than 100% ethanol (34.15 mg GAE/g DW) and 100% acetone extracts (31.92 mg GAE/g DW) (p < 0.01). The TPC values of *C. polygonoides* foliages in different solvent extract ranged from 29.33 mg GAE/g DW in 100% acetone extract to 170.96 mg GAE/g DW in 50% acetone extracts (Table 3), which follows the decreasing trend in different extracts as: 50% acetone > 75% ethanol > 75% methanol > 50% ethanol > 75% acetone > 50% methanol > 100% methanol > water > 100% ethanol > 100% acetone (Fig. 1A). The highest value for TPC in 50% acetone (170.96 mg GAE/g DW) was not significantly higher than 75% ethanol extract (165.23 mg GAE/g DW) whereas, the TPC values for 75% methanol extract (154.18 mg GAE/g DW), 50% ethanol extract (152.69 mg GAE/g DW) and 75% acetone extract (149.42 mg GAE/g DW) were at par to each other (p < 0.01). Similarly, the TPC of flower bud in water extract (85.65 mg GAE/g DW) surpassed the value of 100%

Table 3: Effect of extraction solvent on TPC, TFC and TAA in *C. polygonoides* foliage

Solvent System*	TPC (mg GAE/g)	TFC (mg CE/g)	TAA (mg AAE/g)
Water	85.65 ^F	3.97 ^G	206.58 ^E
Ethanol			
100% ethanol	30.84 ^G	1.36 ^I	78.06 ^F
75% aqueous ethanol	165.23 ^{AB}	6.35 ^C	378.84 ^{AB}
50% aqueous ethanol	152.69 ^{BCD}	6.30 ^C	386.63 ^{AB}
Methanol			
100% Methanol	113.03 ^E	4.45 ^F	351.80 ^{CD}
75% aqueous methanol	154.18 ^{BC}	5.64 ^D	373.72 ^{BC}
50% aqueous methanol	138.11 ^D	5.34 ^E	339.47 ^D
Acetone			
100% acetone	29.23 ^G	1.73 ^H	82.46 ^F
75% aqueous acetone	149.42 ^{CD}	7.01 ^B	365.44 ^{BC}
50% aqueous acetone	170.96 ^A	8.12 ^A	400.23 ^A

*Expressed as fraction of solvents to water. TPC-Total phenolic content; TFC-Total flavonoids content; TTA-Total antioxidant activity; GAE-Gallic acid equivalent; CE-Catechin equivalent; AAE-Ascorbic acid equivalent. Different superscripted letters (A-I) indicate significant difference from one another (p < 0.01)

Fig. 1: Effect of extraction solvent on (A) Total Phenolic Content (TPC), (B) Total flavonoids content (TFC) and (C) Total antioxidant activity (TAA) of *C. polygonoides* flower bud and foliage.

ethanol extract (30.84 mg GAE/g DW) and 100% acetone extract (29.23 mg GAE/g DW). These results are supported with the earlier report of Zlotek *et al.* (29), who reported that acetone based solvent system was more effective in phenolic extraction from *Ocimum basilicum* leaves than methanol based solvent whereas Do *et al.* (30) reported that 100% ethanol was the best extraction solvent for TPC and TFC followed by 100% acetone which is decreased with increase in polarity of the solvent in *Limnophila aromatic* plant.

From the data presented in Tables 2 and 3, it was observed that the highest TPC was recorded in aqueous solvent system (50% acetone, 50% methanol and 75% ethanol) but behaved somewhat differently in flower bud and foliages, while, lowest TPC in non-aqueous solvent system (irrespective of plant tissue) along with pure aqueous extract showed that *C. polygonoides* attributes a blend of polar and non-polar phenolic compounds with low to medium number of phenolic compound. Ebert (24) found that aqueous methanol was better solvent for lower molecular weight phenolics, while aqueous acetone for phenolics with higher molecular weight. Therefore, it can be concluded that flower bud contains lower molecular weight phenolics whereas foliages are rich in higher molecular phenolics. Based on the results of TPC, 50% methanol and 50% acetone are the best TPC extraction solvent for *C. polygonoides* flower bud and foliages, respectively.

Total flavonoids content (TFC): The TFC of flower bud and foliages of *C. polygonoides* in different solvent extracts are reported in Tables 2 and 3. The TFC ranged from 1.4 mg CE/g DW in 100% ethanol extract to 6.03 mg CE/g DW in 50% acetone extract of flower bud (Table 2) and 1.36 mg CE/g DW in 100% ethanol extract to 8.12 mg CE/g DW in 50% acetone extract of foliages (Table 3). Irrespective of the plant tissues, 50% acetone comes out to be the best solvent system for TFC extraction from *C. polygonoides* plant parts followed by 75% acetone with TFC of 5.55 and 7.01 mg CE/g DW and 75% ethanol with TFC of 4.82 and 6.35 mg CE/g DW in flower bud and foliages, respectively (Fig. 1B). Similar to the TPC, 100% ethanol and 100% acetone came out to be the poorest solvent system with TFC of

1.4 and 1.36 mg CE/g DW and of 1.79 and 1.73 mg CE/g DW, respectively in flower bud and foliages with statistically at par to each other while water extracts of flower bud and foliages with TFC of 2.58 and 3.97 mg CE/g DW, respectively, significantly surpassed both the solvents. The effect of polarity of solvent on TFC is almost similar to the TPC but in case of TFC, second best is aqueous ethanol instead of aqueous methanol which performed better in case of TPC.

Total antioxidant activity (TAA): TAA of different extracts was assayed by CUPRAC method which evaluates the sample capacity to reduce the Cu^{2+} to Cu^{1+} in the presence of Neocuproine (chelating agent). This activity was measured spectrophotometrically at 450nm and expressed as ascorbic acid equivalent (AAE/g DW). In *C. polygonoides* flower bud, 50% aqueous acetone extracts exhibited highest TAA followed by extracts of 75% aqueous acetone, 50% aqueous ethanol, 50% methanol, 75% ethanol, 75% methanol, water, 100% acetone and 100% ethanol (Fig. 1C). The TAA of 50% aqueous acetone extract (351.97 mg AAE/g DW) was mathematically higher than 75% aqueous acetone extract (338.21 mg AAE/g DW) and 50% aqueous methanol extract (332.79 mg AAE/g DW) but the difference was statistically non-significant (Table 2). Similarly in foliages, 50% aqueous acetone extracts exhibited highest TAA followed by extracts of 50% aqueous ethanol, 75% aqueous ethanol, 75% aqueous methanol, 75% aqueous acetone, 100% methanol, 50% aqueous methanol, water, 100% acetone and 100% ethanol (Fig. 1C). The TAA of 50% acetone extract (400.23 mg AAE/g DW) was highest but statistically at par with that of 50% aqueous ethanol extract (386.63 mg AAE/g DW) and 75% aqueous ethanol extract (378.84 mg AAE/g DW) and these two were statistically at par with 75% aqueous methanol (373.72 g AAE/g DW) and 75% aqueous acetone (365.44 mg AAE/g DW) (Table 3). Similar to the TPC and TFC, extracts of 100% ethanol and 100% acetone exhibited significantly lowest TAA ($p < 0.01$) followed by water extract (irrespective of the plant tissues). These results are almost similar to previous reports. Turkmen *et al.* (28) reported that mate tea and black tea exhibited highest antioxidant activity

when extracted with 50% aqueous ethanol and 50% aqueous acetone, respectively. These results are also supported by the earlier reports which said that for extraction of phenolics and antioxidant compounds by solvents with intermediate polarity are to be used as compared to those highly polar such as water or non-polar solvents such as hexane (31).

A correlation coefficient was performed on Pearson's scale among TPC, TFC and TAA of flower bud and foliage extracts. The correlation among all three parameters was found to be extremely positive with R^2 values of 0.924, 0.974 and 0.939 between TPC & TFC, TPC & TAA and TFC & TAA, respectively (Table 4). The results indicate that flavonoids are the dominating phenolic groups in *C. polygonoides*. The results are similar with the phenolic extracts from *Ocimum basilicum* leaves (29), *Limnophila aromatic* (30), guava and banana (32).

TPC, TFC and TAA of *C. polygonoides* flower bud and foliages were evaluated in aqueous extract along with different concentrations of ethanol, methanol and acetone (50%, 75% and 100%, respectively). Irrespective of the plant part, TPC, TFC and TAA were increased with increasing water content in organic solvent and even sole water extract had higher TPC, TFC and TAA than 100% acetone extract and 100% ethanol extract. The TPC of the extracts were consistent with TFC and TAA with correlation coefficient of more than 0.92 among all three parameters. By considering the results of TPC, TFC and TAA of *C. polygonoides* flower bud and foliages under different solvent system, it can be concluded that 50% aqueous acetone and 50% aqueous methanol provided significantly better results than those of the other solvent system. Along with these two solvent systems aqueous ethanol also gave at par results for TPC, TFC and TAA in foliages. The results of present investigation indicated that *C. polygonoides* with establishment of an appropriate extraction solvent, could serve as effective drug against oxidative damage

Table 4: Pearson's correlation coefficient among TPC, TFC and TAA

	TPC	TFC	TAA
TPC	1		
TFC	0.924	1	
TAA	0.974	0.938	1

associated with free-radicalas well as natural bio-fortified agent in functional food and nutraceuticals industry.

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References

- Perez-Jimenez J, Arranz, S, Tabernero M, Diaz-Rubio ME, Serrano J, Goni I & Saura-Calixto F (2008) *Food Res Intern*, **41**, 274.
- Amarowicz R, Pegg RB, Rahimi-Moghaddam P, Barl B & Weil JA (2004) *Food Chem*, **84**, 551.
- Balasundram N, Sundram K, Samman S (2006) *Food Chem*, **99**, 191.
- Soto-Vaca A, Gutierrez A, Losso JN, Xu Z & Finley JW (2012) *J Agricul Food Chem*, **60**, 6658.
- Gulcin I & Beydemir S (2013) *Mini-Rev Med Chem*, **13**, 408.
- Skerget M, Kotnik P, Hadolin M, Hras AR, Simonc M & Knez Z (2005) *Food Chem* **89**, 191.
- Bhandari MM (1978) *Flora of the Indian Desert*, Scientific Publishers, Jodhpur, 331.
- Khan TI (1997) *Environ*, **17**, 283.
- Bhandari MM (1990) MPS Repros, Jodhpur, India.
- Bhandari MM (1995) In: *Taxonomy and Biodiversity* (CBS Publishers), Delhi, 29.
- Kumar S, Parveen & Narain P (2005) *Medicinal Plants in Indian Arid Zone*, CAZRI, Jodhpur, 14.
- Goyal M & Sharma SK (2008) *Indian J Trad Knowl*, **8**, 581.
- Mohil P (2013) *Environmental Consciousness and Human Perceptions* (Lambert Academic Publishing), 90.
- Katwa SS & Galav PK (2005) *Indian J Trad Knowl*, **4**, 237.
- Samejo MQ, Memon S, Bhangar MI & Khan KM (2011) *J Pharma Res*, **4**, 4402.
- Khan A, Khan RA, Ahmed M & Mustaq N (2015) *Bangladesh J Pharmacol*, **10**, 316.
- Gomes SMC, Fernandes IPG, Shekhawat NS, Kumbhat S & Oliveira-Brett AM (2015) *Electroanalysis*, **27**, 293.
- Yawer MA, Ahmed E, Malik A, Ashraf M, Rasool MA & Afza N (2007) *Chem Biodiver*, **7**, 1578.
- Berwal MK, Haldhar SM & Saroj PL (2018) *Proc. National Conference of Arid Horticulture* (NCA-2018), ICAR-Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Bikaner (Rajasthan).

- 20 **Bhagwat S, Haytowitz DB & Holden JM** (2014) <http://www.ars.usda.gov/nutrientdata>.
- 21 **Rashi B, Ajai K & Sadhna P** (2011) *Intern J Curr Res*, **3**, 215.
- 22 **Knio KM, Usta J, Dagher S, Zournajian H & Kreydiyyeh S** (2008) *Biores Technol*, **99**, 763.
- 23 **Bhatnagar M, Kapur KK, Jalee S & Sharma SK** (1993) *J Entomol Res*, **17**, 21.
- 24 **Ebert TA, Kevan PG, Bishop BL, Kevan SD & Downer RA** (2007) *J Apicul Res*, **46**, 220.
- 25 **Medini F, Fella H, Ksouri R & Abdelly C** (2014) *J Taibah Univer Sci*, **8**, 216.
- 26 **Apak R, Guclu K, Ozyurek M & Karademir SE** (2004) *J Agricul Food Chem*, **52**, 7970.
- 27 **Harbourne N, Marete E, Jacquier JC & O'Riordan D** (2013) *Food Res Intern*, **50**, 480.
- 28 **Turkmen N, Sari F & Velioglu YS** (2006) *Food Chem*, **99**, 835.
- 29 **Zlotek U, Mikulska S, Nagajek M & Swieca M** (2016) *Saudi J Biol Sci*, **23**, 628.
- 30 **Do QD, Angkawijaya AE., Tran-Nguyen PL, Huynh LH, Soetaredjo FE, Ismadji S & Ju Y-H** (2014) *J Food Drug Anal*, **22**, 296.
- 31 **Adaramola B & Onigbinde A** (2016) *IOSR J Pharma Biol Sci*, **11**, 33.
- 32 **Alothman M, Bhat R & Karim AA** (2009) *Food Chem*, **115**, 785.